

B.R AMBEDKAR AND SOCIAL JUSTICE

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ABSTRACT

Dr. B.R Ambedkar (1891-1956) appeared on the Indian Socio-Political Scene in the early 1920s and Remained at the forefront of the Social, Cultural, Economic and Political transformation of India during the closing decades of the British Rule after India got Freedom He played a very significant role in laying the foundation of modern India till his Death.

Dr. B.R Ambedkar was a great social reformer a valiant champion of social justice and an emancipator of the downtrodden masses of India who dedicated all his life to a waken the social conscience of modern India. His thought that all types of oppressions denial exploitation and injustices can be removed by the state. In this regard he made many provisions in constitution of India for Schedule Caste, Schedule Tribes, Minorities, Children and Women and state has been given duty and responsibility of protecting, promoting and safeguarding the interest of weaker sections of society. In this paper Dr. B.R Ambedkar's dream of social justice are discussed.

Key Words:

State Democracy, Social justice, weaker sections

INTRODUCTION

Dr. B.R Ambedkar is the pioneer of social justice in India has given the vision to overcome inequalities and sufferings of the weaker section and to get dignity and emancipation of untouchability. He was portrayed as a leader for deprived class, but he must be portrayed as a leader for humanity because his notion is always to establish an egalitarian society in India hence he had made social justice as the basic feature of our Indian Constitution. He always wants to bring a balance of wheel between privileged class and deprived class. The Article covers the ideas of Dr. B.R Ambedkar on Social justice. How helpful to uplift the downtrodden people to lead a dignified life based on Liberty, equality and fraternity.

Objectives of the study :

- To introduce in brief the conceptual framework of Social justice.
- To examine and analyze the role of Dr. B.R Ambedkar's reflection in making of Indian Constitution.
- To understand in brief the Dr. B.R Ambedkar's notion of Social justice and its Contemporary relevance.

Methodology:

The present study will be based on the data and sources collected from the secondary sources pertaining to relevant policy documents and policy reports, debates and speeches, books, articles and journals. Further to inquire into ideas of Dr. B.R Ambedkar's reflection in Indian Constitution and notion of Social justice with its contemporary relevance.

Meaning of Social Justice:

Social justice means equal social opportunities shall be available to everyone to develop their personalities which is associated with equality and social rights.

According to Dr. B.R Ambedkar “Social justice is based on moral values and self respect. Justice situates through social, political and economic justices which regulated by the Indian Constitution.

The concept of Social justice has significance in the context of Indian society which is divided into castes and communities as they create walls and barriers of exclusiveness on the basis of superiority and inferiority and these inequalities in turn pose serious threat to Indian democracy.

The concept of Social justice takes within its sweep the objective of removing inequalities and affording equal opportunities to all citizens in social, economic and political affairs.

Dr. B.R Ambedkar’s Vision of Social justice:

According to Dr. B.R Ambedkar the term “Social Justice” is based upon equality, liberty and fraternity of all human beings. The aim of Social justice is to remove all kinds of inequalities based upon caste, race, sex, power, position and wealth. The Social justice brings equal distribution of the social, political and economical resources of the community.

Dr. B.R Ambedkar’s thoughts on Social justice were progressive. He did not believe in violence; he considered the press to be a powerful tool for social changes for justice and freedom. He published Mook Nayak, Janata and Samata magazines, but these magazines remained largely unsold. Perhaps because of the progressive and un conventional thoughts expressed there in. If there are prohibitions on the social evil of untouchability in the constitution. Than this credit goes to Dr. B.R Ambedkar to a great extent. His greatest achievement was that he made the downtrodden of India feel their separate powerful existence; the credit goes to him that he brought all the down trod den, untouchable castes under the one name of SCs. If Dr. B.R Ambedkar had not pursued special reservation facilities for the SCs/STs in the field of education and government services of the central and states governments, their conditions would have remained as before laden with sorrow and sufferings. It is the result of Dr. B.R Ambedkar’s constant efforts that today there are members of Parliament members of the Legislative Assembly. The Indian Administrative Service, The Indian Police Service, Professors and Doctors from among these castes.

Dr. B.R Ambedkar stood for a social system in which man’s status is based on his merit and achievements and where no one is noble or untouchable because of his/her birth. He advocated the policy of preferential treatment for the socially oppressed and economically exploited people of the Country. The constitution of India, which was drafted under his Chairmanship, contains a number of provisions that enjoins the state to secure to all its citizens, justice, social, economic and political, along with liberty, equality and fraternity. It also contains a number of provisions that guarantee a preferential treatment to the downtrodden people in various sectors. Article 17 of the Indian Constitution declares untouchability as abolished. Dr. B.R Ambedkar in his speech before the Constituent Assembly for the passage of the Constitution said “I have completed my work; I wish there should be a sunrise even tomorrow. The new India has got political freedom, but it is yet to raise the sun of social and economic liberty.”

CONCLUSION

Dr. B.R Ambedkar struggled a lot for the realization of an egalitarian society to be based on social democracy. This is visible through his notion been incorporated in Indian Constitution making the provisions and safeguarding the interests of weaker section of society providing them all equal rights

and human dignity. He was aware of the rights of the depressed classes of Indian society and there by demolishing the existing caste practices untouchability and caste based discrimination through making provisions with the constitution.

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